

ORGANIZATION OF EFFECTIVE ACTIVITIES OF THE MANAGER OF WATER AND AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. The article presents the concept of "Knowledge Management"; "Knowledge Management" (KM) is a purposeful organization of the activities of the entire company, where "knowledge" is considered as the main strategic success factor. "Knowledge management" is only an integral part of this global task.

Keywords: manager, management, approach, success, knowledge, innovation, identification, business model, strategy, matrix, incentive, insurance, dividend policy, futures, credit, sustainability.

Introduction. Currently, the issue of the effective activity of the water and agriculture manager is becoming important in the training of personnel. At the same time, the study of knowledge management requires considerable attention to the global nature of the problem of personnel management psychology.

Research methodology. This article suggests important approaches to knowledge management. The participation of specialists from different fields in the development of the concept of knowledge management has led to its complex nature. As a result, three approaches were formed.

Drawing-1.

The concept of "Knowledge": Knowledge is a fundamental resource based on the practical experience of specialists and on the data existing at a particular enterprise.

➤ *Indigenous knowledge is a necessary minimum that ensures "participation in the game".*

➤ *Knowledge that ensures success provides the company with competitive potential.*

➤ *Innovative knowledge gives the company the opportunity to change the "rules of the game". It is they who give the company the opportunity to lead in the industry.*

The place of knowledge in the activities of enterprises; The importance of knowledge management tasks for an enterprise is determined by the level of its managerial maturity and the level of competition in the markets in which it is going to work. So, in order to show the place and value of the knowledge resource, Doug Engelbart proposed the following classification of the functions of the enterprise:

A - primary activity: manufacture of specific products or service

B - secondary activity aimed at improving the main function

C - activities to improve function B

Actions for the implementation and development of knowledge management in the company;

Building a company's business model:

➤ Identification of the company's activities at the strategic, functional and process level.

➤ Identification of "key knowledge"

➤ The choice of the strategy of "knowledge management", its connection with the principles of business functioning.

➤ of key success factors

➤ Linking "knowledge" with company processes: developing knowledge-based management processes into the company's business model

➤ Creation of a technological IT platform for the application of knowledge

➤ Development of an internal culture of knowledge exchange, generation and application of knowledge.

Drawing-2.

Matrix of "knowledge management" strategies.

The car	Search for new patterns in information arrays. Simulation modeling	Formalization and accumulation of knowledge in the corporate database
Person	Activating the personal potential of employees to generate new ideas	Continuous training of employees and transfer of experience
	New	Old

The role of financial management is that it helps the company's management to answer the following practical questions:

1. What amount of financial resources is necessary for the successful operation of the subject in a competitive environment;

2. From what sources can these financial resources be obtained and what is their rational structure;

3. How should operational management of financial resources and capital be carried out to ensure financial stability, profitability and solvency of the enterprise in the short and long term;
4. In what ways can commercial risks arising in current (operational), investment and financial activities be reduced?

Control scheme

The CFO is the highest level after the CEO and provides the necessary and useful information for making managerial decisions of a financial nature.

The finance department in the management of the firm is responsible for analyzing financial problems, making decisions in some cases, or making recommendations to senior management.

The accounting department is engaged in accounting for the turnover of financial resources at the enterprise.

Subjects and methods of FM

- General economic
- Predictive and analytical
- Special

General economic conditions are the possibility or obligation of execution, are set centrally within the framework of the system of state management of the economy. These include: lending, loan operations, cash and settlement operations, insurance, financial sanctions system, trust and transfer operations, collateral operations, depreciation deduction system, taxation system, etc.

Forecasting and analytical includes financial planning, tax planning, forecasting methods, factor analysis and modeling.

Special methods – dividend policy, financial lease, factoring operations, franchising, futures, etc.

Drawing-3.

Careful business financing, a conscious combination of benefits and risks when using external sources of financing (financial activity of the enterprise).

Making a profit from current activities due to the efficient use of all labor resources (operating activities of the enterprise).

Selection and use of investments based on reasonable economic analysis and management (investment activity of the enterprise).

Qualification characteristics FM

The qualification characteristic of a financial manager imposes requirements on him in the field of his theoretical training and practical skills of work.

«Must know»

1. Management theory.
2. Theory of finance, credit and money circulation.
3. The theory of financial management.
4. Accounting.
5. Economic statistics.
6. The main regulatory and legislative acts on international settlements and foreign economic activity.
7. Types of securities and the procedure for their circulation.
8. Rules and procedure for conducting transactions in the domestic financial market.
9. Fundamentals of transactions in the international financial market.
10. Fundamentals of the economy of an economic entity.
11. Methodology and methodology of economic analysis.
12. Office work and correspondence.

«Must be able to»

1. Read the balance sheet.
2. Understand the statistical, accounting and operational reporting of the subject.
3. Understand financial information.
4. Analyze the results of production, trade and especially financial activities of the subject.
5. Analyze and evaluate the economic efficiency of capital investment measures.
6. Predict the results of capital investment.
7. Develop programs for the use of financial resources.
8. Make a financial plan.
9. Prepare a report on the use of financial resources and the implementation of financial plan indicators.
10. Prepare documents on financial issues to the bank, the tax service and other management bodies.
11. To monitor the implementation of the indicators of the financial plan, financial programs, the effective use of financial resources, fixed assets, intangible assets, working capital.

Local FM tasks

1. Formation of financial resources in volume.
2. Ensuring the rational use of the generated amount of financial resources.

3. Optimization of cash flows.
4. Obtaining an acceptable amount of operating profit.
5. Achieving a minimum level of commercial risk.
6. Ensuring sufficient financial stability and solvency of the enterprise in the process of its development.
7. Increasing the value of the company.
8. Achieving financial flexibility of the enterprise.

Conclusions: The essence and solutions of the proposed

1. Sufficient for the current and future development of the enterprise.
2. In the context of the main activities of the enterprise.
3. As well as the inflow and outflow of money in current, investment and financial activities.
4. Profit from sales at a given level of commercial risk.
5. To get an acceptable amount of profit.
7. Due to the growth of the market price of its shares on the organized stock market.
8. As its ability to quickly generate the necessary amount of money when highly effective financial proposals or new opportunities for economic growth suddenly appear.

REFERENCES

1. A. K. Semenov, E. L. Maslova, Psychology and ethics of management and business., Dashkov and K, 2006. p. 40-42
2. V. L. Polukarov, V. I. Petrushin; Moscow Institute of Management, Psychology of Management, (KNORUS, 2008)
3. E. P. Ilyin, Motivation and motives, St. Petersburg, 2008. p. 66.